

WP4: Deepening through improved processes and tools for trans-national cooperation

Theme 2: Creating more opportunities for trans-national funding collaboration

Deliverable 4: Addressing barriers to collaboration

1. Introduction

Within the Euphresco I project, a report on mapping and analysis of national phytosanitary research programmes was delivered (DL 2.2 Euphresco I). This extensive report was based on a questionnaire filled in by the partners at that time. Amongst many other questions, partners were asked to comment upon their barriers with respect to transnational research.

The main identified obstacles were limited or unavailable funds, legal issues, financial inflexibility, timing issues, inconsistency with respect to the programme rationale, issues concerning intellectual property rights and language problems.

Within Euphresco II, new partners and observers joined the network, and “old” partners gained experience and trust in transnational research. In order to define recommendations to partners on how to increase their capacity towards transnational cooperation, a detailed questionnaire was developed specifically to identify barriers and to collect suggestions on how to overcome them. The design of the questionnaire was inspired by the outcome of the Euphresco I analysis, and the questionnaire developed within the CORE-Organic ERA-NET.

The questionnaire was presented at the project meeting in Lisbon (March 2013). Part of the questionnaires were filled in during the meeting, others were submitted in a later stage.

2. Questionnaire

The questionnaire is presented on pages 2 to 7. It is divided into a set of generic questions Q1 to Q7 followed by specific questions on identification of barriers Q8 to Q18, subdivided into barriers towards the different funding mechanisms (Real Common Pot: RP, Virtual Common Pot: VP and Non-Competitive Mechanism: NC).

Q7 is only indirectly linked to the assessment of barriers, but was added at the request of the WP3 leader in order to evaluate the web-tool for project initiation and selection.

Space for extra comments was foreseen for each question as well as after each set of questions. Comments to specific questions are given in the attached Excel file (2 sheets) and the main tendencies are retaken in this document, as well as the more general comments.

Questionnaire EUPHRESKO II: Addressing barriers to collaboration

Background:

Identification and systematic mapping of the individual EUPHRESKO-II's partners barriers to trans-national research.

Aim: Recommendations to EUPHRESKO-II partners on how to increase their own capacity to improve transnational cooperation, including funding.

Questions		Answers: <i>thick the appropriate answer with X</i>	Comments
Q1	Are you already involved in transnational research?	... No ... Yes Via ... Euphresco ... EU-Framework Programs ... International programs ... Regional programs ... Others (specify)	
Q2	Is the call you are involved in evaluated transnationally?	... No ... Yes If yes, indicate evaluation methodology	
Q3	Is the research progress evaluated transnationally?	... No ... Yes	

		If yes, indicate evaluation methodology	
Q4	What is the benefit/relevance of having a transnational program ?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... Capacity building ... Underpinning regional policy ... Underpinning national policy ... Underpinning international policy ... Strategic interest ... Economic interest ... Other (specify) 	
Q5	Are you mainly involved in funding or in funding combined to program execution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... Not applicable ... Funding ... Funding and execution 	
Q6	Which type of funding mechanism can you use in the Euphresco projects ?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... Not applicable ... Real Common Pot ... Virtual Common Pot ... Non-competitive Mechanism ... Other (specify) 	
Q7	Is the web-based project initiation/selection procedure clear to you?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ... No ... Yes 	
General comments / remarks			

		Real common pot	Virtual common pot	Non-competitive	Suggestion on how to overcome these barriers	Level of difficulty to overcome these barriers through the suggested action	Comments
Q8	Legal barriers	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)		... Almost unfeasible ... Feasible, but difficult ... Feasible, not too difficult ... Feasible, easy	
Q9	Administrative barriers	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)		... Almost unfeasible ... Feasible, but difficult ... Feasible, not too difficult ... Feasible, easy	
Q10	Political barriers	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)		... Almost unfeasible ... Feasible, but	

						difficult ... Feasible, not too difficult ... Feasible, easy	
Q11	Financial barriers	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)		... Almost unfeasible ... Feasible, but difficult ... Feasible, not too difficult ... Feasible, easy	
Q12	Barriers with respect to timing annual round proposals	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)		... Almost unfeasible ... Feasible, but difficult ... Feasible, not too difficult ... Feasible, easy	
Q13	Barriers with respect to timing incorporate emergencies	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)		... Almost unfeasible ... Feasible, but difficult ... Feasible, not too difficult ... Feasible, easy	
Q14	Barriers with respect to	... No ... Yes	... No ... Yes	... No ... Yes		... Almost unfeasible	

	capacity of research and infrastructure(specify)(specify)(specify)		... Feasible, but difficult ... Feasible, not too difficult ... Feasible, easy	
Q15	Barriers with respect to program rationale: strategically incompatible	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)		... Almost unfeasible ... Feasible, but difficult ... Feasible, not too difficult ... Feasible, easy	
Q16	Barriers with respect to program rationale: economically incompatible	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)		... Almost unfeasible ... Feasible, but difficult ... Feasible, not too difficult ... Feasible, easy	
Q17	Barriers with respect to Intellectual Property Rights	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)	... No ... Yes(specify)		... Almost unfeasible ... Feasible, but difficult ... Feasible, not too difficult ... Feasible, easy	
Q18	Not finding a	... No	... No	... No		... Almost	

	topic coordinator	... Yes(specify)	... Yes(specify)	... Yes(specify)		unfeasible ... Feasible, but difficult ... Feasible, not too difficult ... Feasible, easy	
General comments / remarks							

3. Analysis

3.1 Response rate

17 out of the 31 partners (from 22 countries) completed the questionnaire; hence a response rate of 55 % was accomplished. We did not check yet how many respondents are ‘new’ partners in euphresco II and if their answers had an influence on the outcome of this survey.

3.2 Partner scene

Generic questions 1 to 6 were included in order to situate the respondents’ current involvement in transnational research.

Only 1 out of the 17 respondents is currently not involved in transnational research. 15 respondents are already involved in Euphresco projects; from which the majority also participate in other international research programmes (figure 1).

Figure 1 (Q1)

The majority of the respondents are partners that have in-house research facilities (Q5: research execution); only 6 out of the 17 respondents are “pure” funders. One respondent filled out the questionnaire but claimed not to be a funder of research, and because of this unclear position, its input was not registered here.

Partners indicated the main drivers for transnational research being capacity building, strategic interest and the underpinning of national and international policy (figure 2).

Figure 2 (Q4)

About half of the respondents report a transnational evaluation of their project proposals, while the research progress itself is evaluated to a lesser extent (figure 3). The relatively high number of non-(transnational) evaluated project proposals is likely to be explained by the Non-Competitive (NC) funding mechanism being the predominant one in the Euphresco portfolio.

Figure 3 (Q2-3)

Almost all of the respondents have the possibility to participate in non-competitive (NP) projects, while the Virtual Common Pot (VP) is appropriate for only 9 out of 17 respondents. The Real Common Pot fits only 2 partners (figure 4).

Figure 4 (Q6)

The web-tool for project initiation and selection was found to be clear to 14 of 17 respondents, and unclear to 2 of them. One partner reported it to be very satisfactory.

3.3 Barriers

3.3.1 Legal barriers

A large number of respondents indicated legal barriers towards participation in the RP, a few towards the VP and only 1 towards the NC projects (figure 5). For many partners, legal barriers towards RP cannot be overcome.

It was commented that some funds have national earmarks and can then only be allocated to a VP. One partner, who was not able to participate in Euphresco projects up till now, is currently adapting its legislation to be able to participate in VP calls from 2014 onwards.

Figure 5 (Q8)

3.3.2 Administrative barriers

From an administrative point of view, the NC mechanism is the easiest of all, and so does not implicate any barrier towards transnational cooperation (figure 6). One partner suggested to simplify bureaucracy as a solution to administrative barriers toward RP and VP. It probably refers to the bureaucracy inside the country? To one respondent's opinion, the RP mechanism will take time to implement. If interpret correctly, one partner launched the idea that, if Euphresco will be hosted in EPPO in the future, an earmarked portion of the annual membership fee could be used to fund a RP project. One partner stated that the public accounting system has to be modified in order to be able to participate more easily in RP and VP projects.

Figure 6 (Q9)

3.3.3 Political barriers

6 respondents indicated political barriers towards RP funding, whereas only 2 towards the VP mechanism and none towards NC funding (figure 7). It was noted that RP funding can only be widely politically accepted when all partners participate in this mechanism, while this is for the moment being not at all the case. Some partners indicated that the “outsourcing” of the countries’ money is politically not acceptable, and not a priority in the present political scenario.

Figure 7 (Q10)

3.3.4 Financial barriers

Several partners reported budget restrictions as being a barrier to mainly RP and VP funding (figure 8). One respondent explained that only part of the budget can be used for RP funding.

It was also pointed out that the annual research budget is not increased because of transnational funding, so to justify the use of the budget for transnational instead of pure national research, there have to be clear benefits. This means that the national partner has to have access to the results of all partners via a final report that can be used to underpin the (national and international) policy.

One partner warns that the noticeable tendency to diminish the contributions to the transnational projects negatively influences the obtainment of a “big” national envelope to participate in the transnational projects where the other partners only contribute with rather small funds.

Figure 8 (Q11)

3.3.5 Barriers towards the timing of the annual round

For all three of the funding mechanisms, the timing of the annual round of research initiation and evaluation seems to be a barrier towards funding of transnational research (figure 9). Partners indicate that it is difficult because it often does not match the national project selection and commissioning scheme. The negotiation time should be longer? Shorter? One respondent suggested a minimum of six months for the negotiation and contract phase. For some, the period for final decision should be shifted to July rather than the end of the year.

Two partners raised the timing issues when using mixed NC/VP system. The NC part can start early before the VP has finished the competition. This disequilibrium can be an issue for the NC partners in the mixed funding system.

Figure 9 (Q12)

3.3.6 Barriers towards the timing of emergencies

A similar picture of barriers towards timing of an “emergency” project is seen compared to the “normal” annual round projects (figure 10). However, the non-competitive projects seem to be more fit for application in case of emergencies, taking into account the minimal administrative load. As VP and peer review of project proposals takes time, some exemptions have to be made in case of emergencies, in order to have a response time as short as possible.

Nevertheless, several partners pointed on restricted budgets so it is not sure appropriate budgets can be redirected for emergencies. One partner refers to the emergency scheme that is also being developed within WP4; once this is finished, it has to be used as a basis for a discussion with the national authorities, and complemented with a national sub planning.

The issue of the mixed NC/VP system is raised again as mentioned above.

Figure 10 (Q13)

3.3.7 Barriers due to research & infrastructure capacities

A few partners indicated research & infrastructure capacity as a barrier to transnational research, approximately to the same (relative) extend for all funding mechanisms. It was indicated that for “pure” funders, the providers’ research and infrastructure capacity needs to be checked before topic proposals can be developed or joined. One respondent reported understaffing, as plant health remains a relatively small section within the domestic agricultural economy. This problem can only be overcome by legal requirements (i.e. EU) facilitating increased staffing.

3.3.8 Barriers towards the programme rationale

Only 1 respondent reported the Euphresco programme rationale not to fit its economic interest. Several partners experienced (part of) the programme to be strategically inappropriate, as it is not always in line with their national strategic plan. Others commented that Euphresco calls cover a broad range of organisms that, in general, are relevant for the national or general programme.

It was suggested to build in enough flexibility in programming in order to be able to react on new emergencies.

3.3.8 Barriers towards Intellectual Property Rights

Some partners struggle with IPR issues towards transnational funding, depending on the type of project. It is reported that the IPR management is unclear for the moment, and that rules should be put in place, including those concerning access rights. Two partners felt that funders should stay owner of their own work in any case.

One partner stressed that final scientific reports with contributions from all partners should be generated and distributed. Currently, as NC projects are built on a voluntary basis, scientific reporting is lacking or running late. Rules have to be defined.

3.3.9 Barriers towards assignment of a topic coordinator

Some partners find it difficult to find a topic coordinator. Indicated reasons are of different origin:

the overall high work pressure makes it difficult to set this additional task of being a coordinator,

in case the funder is also a research executor, is it commented that this could lead to a conflict of interest,

in case of a “pure” funder, it is believed to be difficult task since the coordinator is then often a policy officer instead of a researcher. It is asked if this can be, to a certain extent, be delegated to a scientist in charge of the scientific execution of the work.

3.4 General remarks

One “pure funder partner” pointed out some differences between pure funders and funders that have their own research facilities: research executers can fund NC projects more easily, can easily define their own capacity and do not need VP/peer review. They can act quicker and therefore they have to wait for the “pure” funders/NPPO partners, these have to follow more stringent and time taking procedures for funding allocation. “research partners” can also be assigned as topic coordinator much more easily.

A partner experienced that in general, in Euphresco there is not much interest for VP funding and peer reviewing proposals, while it are the preferred mechanisms for this partner. The partner also raised the question of scientific quality which is an essential aspect although not guaranteed when working on a voluntary basis via NC funding.

Another “research partner” noticed that they have the potential to participate in non-competitive projects, but would rather avoid such a funding mechanism.

It is noted that in general, in euphresco there is not much interest for VP and peer reviewing proposals, and that can be a barrier. This brings also the question of scientific quality which is not guaranteed when working on a voluntary basis via NC funding.

One partner considers ERA-NET projects the only transnational projects where they can play a relevant role. He appointed the national research agency most suited for VP funding.

One partner wants to encourage the use and development of the web-based “market place”.

One partner warned for imbalanced financial participation of the different partners within the same research project which could have an impact on the readiness of a national partner to provide an important fund into a collaborative project.

One partner revealed that the Euphresco organisation sends out a lot of information to its partners, which is not always relevant for a particular partner. It is suggested that a more targeted communication is set up, taking into account the funding mechanisms in which partners are involved.

3.5 Conclusions and recommendations

With a response rate of about 55 %, the questionnaire on barriers is suitable to evaluate the current status of involvement and obstacles towards transnational funding, and to consider thoughts on how to address part of them.

The Euphresco consortium consists of partners being “pure funders” and others that are able to execute the research themselves. Both groups have different interests in the transnational research, and have different funding possibilities. What is a barrier for a “pure funder”, can be an incentive for a partner who can provide research within its own organization, and *vice versa*. Therefore, the Euphresco consortium should stimulate at least both NC and VP funding, and should set up rules for mixed NC/VP funding. In general, a balance should be sought to satisfy the needs and requirements of both groups, concerning either call, evaluation and reporting procedures.

NC funding is found to be the most easy, flexible and quick way of transnational research funding. However, it does not suit every Euphresco partner (especially pure funders) because it lacks competition and peer review of proposals.

Although many partners have the possibilities to participate in a Virtual Pot funding, this is only exploited to a limited level. Future calls should therefore consider taking VP mechanisms, or mixed NC/VP mechanisms forward.

Participation in Euphresco projects needs flexibility regarding timing and procedure, so it is necessary to adapt national legislation and procedures in order to be as flexible as possible. However, this should not imply a loss of scientific quality and value of the end product in relation to the goal of underpinning policy on a national and international level.

Concerning the programme rationale, quite a few partners felt that it is currently lacking topics in line with the national strategic plan. It is recommended that those partners identify their needs during the phase of topic identification. It can be a topic for WP5 and the broadening of the network.

Regarding emergencies, partners should consider a national emergency procedures to be developed based upon the scheme proposed within WP4, in order to be able to provide appropriate transnational research activities in due time. Here again, partners that can combine their funding with research execution seem to be the most flexible to react on emergencies.

Recommendations towards partners not participating yet

Partners that do not participate yet are encouraged to do so, starting with a small contribution towards a project funded under the most appropriate mechanism. After gaining trust, funding budgets can be raised and other mechanisms can be explored. It is recommended that intense consultation is organized with the national authorities, research providers and other relevant stakeholders in order to contribute in a way that is widely supported. The Euphresco annual meeting provides an excellent forum for exchange of ideas and sharing of experiences.

Recommendations towards partners already participating in transnational research

It was recommended for “pure research funders” to invest reasonable funds in a few projects rather than small funds in a lot of projects in order to avoid excessive fragmentation that potentially result in poor scientific output. On the other hand, partners that are also research executors make their own choice and allocate their finances according to the engagement in the projects. Also, some NC projects (e.g. ring testing) do not require big funds and can perfectly be of high quality.

VP as well as NC coordinators should insist on the delivery of a scientific end report that can be valorized to enhance science and to support regional, national or international policy, and that can be consulted by the Euphresco community.

Recommendations toward the Network Management Group / call secretariat

The network management group should define clear rules on peer review of proposals, reporting, intellectual property and access rights for all funding mechanisms. Procedures and tools for mixed funding (NC/VP) should be developed.

The future call secretariat should promote multiple funding mechanisms in order to meet the needs of all partners and stakeholders.